

SOME COMMENTS ON THE POSSIBILITIES OF SPEECH TONE

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Abstract. One of the main functions of any language is communicative - the exchange of information, when expressing this function, different units work together. In our article, we tried to analyze the possibilities of tone, which takes on a great burden of conveying to the interlocutor the purpose of the oral communication process, using various examples.

Key words: sociability, communication, language, oral speech, verbal communication, tone, intonation.

Various studies have shown that in modern linguistics, tone is an essential tool for performing a variety of tasks as the most essential part of live speech. In fact, the main purpose that leads to the emergence of tone speech communication - from the exchange of information (communicative task) to the various instantaneous and individual characteristics of the interlocutors in the speech process - mental, emotional, physical condition, age, gender, nationality, culture, profession or is a multifaceted linguistic nonverbal phenomenon that can reflect the characteristics of the profession (emotional-expressive function). These signs of melody can be clearly seen by observing the speeches of the protagonists of the work of art.

For example, *Gapingiz to 'g'ri. Sharoit zo'r. Xohlagan qing'irliklarga shart-sharoit mixday yaratilgan, buni biz bilamiz, — Omonullo «biz» degan so'zni alohida urg'u bilan talaffuz etdi. Bu alohida ohang boshliqning miyasiga to'qmoqdek urilib, bir seskandi. Lekin o'zini go'llikka solib, xi-xilab kuldi:*

— Iye, hali shunaqalar ham bormi? Qing'irlikdan Xudo asrasin. Hukumat shuncha sharoit yaratib berganiga shukur qilib to'g'ri ishlaganga nima yetsin! [3]

A "special tone" emphasizing "us" was needed to fully express the meaning and discursive purpose of Amanullah's speech. Because the protagonist was referring not

only to himself, but also to the police officers behind him. There was a sense of dread in the tone of the "boss" and the meaning behind that "special tone". So, without this tone, Amanullah would not have been able to express the purpose of his speech clearly and would not have had such an impact on the boss.

The unity of the interrelated components of speech tone, such as speed, duration, consistency, rise or fall, is intonation, which is one of the components of the prosodic system of language. Unlike other linguistic units, it is a nonverbal prosodic unit capable of forming not only the sentence but also the expressive meaning of speech.

Phrase stress is one of the most important components of intonation, which helps to change the tone of a sentence and adapt it to the purpose of speech. For example, in interrogative sentences, a phrase is used to distinguish the word or combination of the sentence that is most interesting to the speaker: *Kecha Komila keldi?* or *Komila kecha keldi?*

In Russian linguistics, intonation is semantic (adaptation of a sentence according to the purpose of speech); expressive (adaptation of speech based on the speaker's emotions); syntactic (representing the specificity of the linguistic syntactic units of a sentence); functions such as euphonics (strength or weakness of speech tone depending on the purpose of speech).

Until the middle of the twentieth century, interest in the relationship between syntax and tone in Russian linguistics increased attempts to define the function of intonation and its components. As a result of these studies, E.A. Brizgunova studied the peculiar intonation of the Russian language in the 1960s and suggested describing intonational constructions in speech. As a result, seven intonation constructions (IC) were developed, which are characteristic of the spoken intonation of the Russian language. These constructions are still in use today.

Depending on the nature of the language, the intonation may vary from language to language. Foreign language learners may find it difficult to adapt to new

speech patterns. During the speech, the speaker's anger, hatred, love, humor, or sarcasm are expressed in intonation. It is not uncommon for new language learners to misunderstand or apply these expressions to speech. This means that intonation is the most characteristic phonetic feature of a language.

The most common function of intonation is the communicative phase. Because language's intonation system is more mobile than grammar, intonation has more potential to respond directly to communication goals. The closest connection between the meaning and intonation of a sentence makes it one of the most important factors in communication. An intonation can tell whether a word is complete or incomplete, whether it contains questions, answers, and so on.

Intonation, combined with the appropriate grammatical structure and lexical structure of a sentence, is an important means of expressing the meaning of pronunciation. Studies by foreign linguists have argued that intonation is a subjective phenomenon, and that different speakers may read the same text differently. In fact, the difference in reading units can be significant. Because different readings can change the meaning of the text. Different intonations of the same text are the result of different interpretations by different readers. The same sentence can be pronounced with different intonations. And each time the intonation of the speech may take on a slightly different meaning. [2]

In enumerating the above functions of tone and intonation, we find it appropriate to dwell on its place in the formation of syntactic units of linguistics.

Speech is the basic unit that people use to communicate with each other, the simplest form of expression. It is a means of communication for the speaker, information for the listener, a means of receiving information.

In human thought, a set of thoughts arises through concepts, and in speech is expressed as a thought. Speech is formed through the use of words, phrases and grammatical forms to convey these ideas and concepts in the form of information.

Speech is caused by a variety of factors, one of which is the tone of the speech. One of the important features of a sentence is that it has a complete tone.

The intellectual and syntactic completeness of a sentence requires both completeness and integrity in terms of tone: a completed tone signifies the completeness of thought and syntactic construction. After all, one of the important differences between speech and non-speech speech is that it has an incomplete tone.

Tone is important not only in determining the completion of a sentence, but also in determining the different type of sentence. This means that whether a word is a noun or a sentence, only the tone of the speech indicates the nature of the word. In addition, other factors may or may not be involved in determining the type of sentence according to the purpose of expression, but the phonetic factor must be the tone.

Tone also plays an important role in the relationship between parts of speech. In the sentences *Men – men, sen – sen* the tone plays a decisive role in distinguishing the parts of speech (possessive-cut) and in showing the relationship between them.

One of the phrases that make up a sentence is also determined by the order and tone of the conjunctions. In this case, the tone is the factor that determines the dependence of the member of the compound.

Structurally and structurally, parts of speech are separated by a short pause in speech. Such passages are called syntagmas, and the pause that separates them is also a form of speech tone. A syntagma is a grammatically and semantically rounded phonetic unit that is pronounced with a single air stroke. The syntagm can be a single word or multiple words. Syntags vary depending on the purpose of the speaker, which means that everyone can say the same thing differently. This stems from the purpose of their speech.

The melody is also involved in connecting the parts of speech. Often, it rises to the level of a grammatical substitute: *Biz ishonamiz – ko 'nglimiz to 'q*. In this case, the melody is used as a connecting link [1].

From this it can be said that melody is a multifunctional and multifaceted medium that, like other units, plays a central role in language.

References:

1. Sayfullayeva R., Mengliyev B., Raupova L., Qurbonova M., Abuzalova M., Yuldasheva D. Hozirgi o‘zbek tili. Darslik. – Buxoro: Durdona, 2021.–555 b.
2. Пронникова Н.В. К вопросу о функцияинтонации//Фундаментальные исследования. Журнал. elibrary.ru
- 3.Тоҳир Малик. Мурдалар гапирмайдилар (қисса). <https://n.ziyouz.com>
4. qizi Cholliyeva G. T. Intonology-An Independent Field of Linguistics //scientist. – 2012. – №. 9. – С. 182-185.
5. Yuldasheva D. N. BASIC NON-VERBAL COMPONENTS OF SPEECH //CURRENT RESEARCH JOURNAL OF PHILOLOGICAL SCIENCES (2767-3758). – 2022. – Т. 3. – №. 01. – С. 17-24.
6. кызы Чуллиева, Гульчехра Тошпулот; ,OHANG SITUATIV PRAGMATIK TIZIM BIRLIGI SIFATIDA, МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫЙ ЖУРНАЛ ИСКУССТВО СЛОВА,4,1-2,,2021.